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Why Culture Must Be Funded with Meaning, Criteria, and Respect for the Public

National Culture Day (in Romania and beyond) is not merely a date on the calendar, nor a ritual repeated year after year with the same predictable speeches. It is—or should be—the moment when we turn our gaze toward everything Romania has produced of greatest value throughout history: ideas, visions, discoveries, creations, and people who have changed the world. Culture is not a museum where we preserve exhibits behind glass; it is a living organism, shaped by poets who sensed the cosmos before physicists did, by musicians who transformed identity into a universal language, by inventors who elevated the dream of flight to the status of science and art, and by scholars who opened pathways to subtle, unseen worlds.

Culture as Vision: From Eminescu’s Stars to the Flight of Vuia and Vlaicu

National Culture Day is not about pageantry, but about value—about those who looked beyond the horizon of their own time and saw what others would only discover much later.

Eminescu stands as the symbol of this day not because tradition demands it, but because in “*To a Star*” he captures, with astonishing poetic intuition, the idea that the light we see now left long ago, perhaps from a star that no longer exists. An idea that would, decades later, become part of the foundations of relativity and modern cosmology. Eminescu did not merely write poetry; through symbol, metaphor, and language, he touched what science would later prove mathematically. More than that, Eminescu’s light is symbolic—a guiding beacon for future generations.

Likewise, Enescu did not simply compose music. In his rhapsodies, he transformed the sounds of these lands into a universal energy. He turned tradition into modernity, identity into art, and local emotion into a language understood across Europe.

But national culture does not stop at poetry and music. It also includes technological courage, scientific vision, and the audacity to reinvent the world.

Aurel Vlaicu, Traian Vuia, and Henri Coandă elevated the dream of flight to the status of both art and science. They were not just inventors; they were composers of the future. Vlaicu transformed wood and canvas into aviation. Vuia proved to the world that a heavier-than-air machine could take off under its own power. Coandă discovered the effect that bears his name and changed aerodynamics forever. And Hermann Oberth—the Sibiu-born pioneer who would become one of the founding fathers of modern rocketry—carried this dream even further. Without him, the path toward space—and today, toward interstellar exploration—would have looked very different.

This is national culture: the place where poetry meets science, music meets technology, and dreams meet reality.

From Heritage to Responsibility: The Lesson of Authentic Value

All these spirits—from Eminescu and Enescu to Vuia, Vlaicu, and Oberth—shared something essential: they created real, recognized, verifiable value. They changed the world not through speeches, but through results. Not through positions, but through vocation. Their culture was not a privilege, but a contribution. Not a ritual, but a living force.

And this lesson of authentic value obliges us today to look very carefully at how we fund culture, especially in times of hardship. If we truly wish to honor the legacy of our noble predecessors, perhaps we should ask ourselves how we support contemporary culture: on the basis of merit or on the basis of inertia? On the basis of real impact or on the basis of habit?

This is where the discussion about meritocracy begins.

Cultural Meritocracy — Between Public Responsibility and the Truth of Numbers

In a Venice bathed in the trembling glow of lanterns, deep into a Carnival night, the avatar of Antonio Vivaldi crosses a narrow piazzetta, surrounded by a strange, almost motionless crowd. The masks, though countless, all bear the same expression: the same frozen smile, the same faded color, the same impenetrable shape. From a platform with a balustrade that, for a moment, seems to warp like a glitch in a virtual matrix, a single voice endlessly repeats the same musical phrase—an ostinato that defies seasons, rhythm, and the very breath of the city itself. No variation, no improvisation, no flicker of freedom. A dystopia reduced to a single mask, a single voice, a single theme. Had such an almost Gothic night been real, even Vivaldi's *Seasons* would have lost their plurality, reaching us as an excessively prolonged monody.

But who, one may ask, hides beneath these masks, and what kind of cultural impunity allows them to traverse centuries without ever being replaced? the pilgrim wondered, rhetorically, in his Dantesque dream...

As a Simple Music Lover, and as a Musicologist

As a simple music lover, I have attended numerous concerts. Strictly within my personal experience—and I emphasize this explicitly: a personal experience, with no claim to being a sociological study or an exhaustive analysis—I have encountered situations in which artistic performances in public institutions were held in halls that were half empty, or even less so. And as a doctor of music, I cannot help but wonder—again, at a purely personal level—how it is possible that certain modernist works presented there can claim to “pleasantly tickle the ear,” to paraphrase Caragiale's famous formulation.

This is precisely why I believe we need clear benchmarks. Data. Serious sociological research. Transparent criteria that show us where there is real dialogue with the public, where there is genuine creative energy, where relevance truly exists. Because in the absence of such instruments, cultural funding risks being driven by inertia rather than by impact.

Culture does not exist outside the economy. Culture is part of the economy. And every public leu invested must generate value—artistic, social, educational, or economic. And let us not forget: this money is taxpayers' money—the money of elderly people carefully budgeting

their pensions, of the business sector that understands its own constraints better than anyone, of ours, of everyone's.

That is why the question is not whether culture should be funded. The answer to that is obvious: YES. The real question is how we fund it. According to what criteria. With what objectives. With what indicators of relevance. Because the difference between a living culture and a self-referential one is, I believe, clearly visible: in full stadiums pulsating with life and joy, or in solemn halls with unsold tickets and empty seats.

History shows us clearly that cultural prosperity has never been the result of chance. Venice flourished not only because of trade, but also because it knew how to invest intelligently in art, in diversity, and in public relevance. In Florence, the Medici family understood that art is not a fiefdom, but added value: they supported popular artists and visions rooted in the ethos of the community, because they knew that collective resonance is part of the city's well-being.

Conclusion: Culture Is Not Celebrated. Culture Is Sustained.

National Culture Day is not an exercise in memory, but an exercise in responsibility. It is not only about Eminescu and Enescu, about Vuia, Vlaicu, Coandă, or Oberth. It is also about the military heroes who sacrificed themselves so that today we can even have a National Culture Day. It is about Valter Măracineanu, Ecaterina Teodoroiu, and Ion Dumitrache. And just as much, it is about the Romanian heroes and veterans of the theaters of operations in Afghanistan—those who carried the tricolor into conflict zones and defended, far from home, the values that define us as a nation.

National culture is our common good, belonging to all of us. It belongs to those who think, create, work, dream, and contribute to the forward movement of society. In this sense, Romanian culture breathes the same air as the great European traditions—the same spirit of freedom, human dignity, and solidarity that has shaped our continent.

Cultural Europe is not an abstraction; it is a community of values. It is the place where Beethoven wrote the "*Ode to Joy*" as a hymn to human fraternity, not to privilege. It is the place where culture does not divide, but unites. It does not build walls, but opens gates. It

does not create castes, but builds bridges. And Romania, through its unique people, has been—and remains—part of this great family of unity in diversity.

If we want this day to truly have meaning, then we must fund culture in its full breadth: art that moves us, science that innovates, technology that opens new paths, festivals that bring communities together, research that creates added value, and projects that fill both concert halls and stadiums. A living culture—accessible, relevant, unafraid to be popular when necessary and profound when required.

Culture is not celebrated once a year.

Culture is sustained.